

here: Appendix for the Application of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc for
The National Scholarship Programme (NSP) of the Slovak Republic,
for the research stay at the *Matej Bel University, Faculty of Natural Science,*
Department of Geography, Geology and Landscape Ecology, Banská Bystrica
Duration: Two months, from the 01st of July 2012 until 01st of September 2012

Research Plan

for the research stay of the visiting researcher Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc in *Matej Bel University, Faculty of Natural Science, Department of Geography, Geology and Landscape Ecology,* in time span of 01 July 2012 - 01 September 2012, under the supervision of Doc. RNDr. Alfonz Gajdoš.

Research topic: Environmental changes in landscapes of Tatra Mountains, Slovakia

Region of Interest: **Tatra Mountains, Slovakia**

Research main aims: **1) Environmental mapping of highlands in Tatra Mountains**
2) Analysis of land cover changes in mountain ecosystems

Expected results:

- Analysis of the landscape and land cover changes in Tatra region, in the past 10-20 years
- One scientific article for the publication in scientific journal specialized on Natural sciences, resuming the results of the research work
- Thematic maps of the landscape dynamic in Tatra mountains
- Report for the NSP resuming results of the research work

Detailed research plan (scheduled on two-week periods)

§ 1. 01 July – 15 July: Data collection and organizing

- 1) Research aim: Using various material sources from both the main Library of *Matej Bel University* and the archives of the *Department of Geography, Geology and Landscape Ecology* we plan to study physical geography, geomorphology and environment in the Tatra Mountains including land use and land cover types, hydrological network and vegetation coverage.
- 2) Technical background: The main software for raster processing would be *ILWIS* (<http://www.ilwis.org/>). The *ArcGIS* will be used as well, if available.
- 3) Paper maps and resources: all possible available materials from the *Faculty of Natural Science*, - detailed maps, books, reports and articles focusing on the region of interest.
- 4) GIS Open source geodata sources: The geodata sources for the analysis of the landscape changes include aerial and satellite images for different time period (10-20 years). The available open sources will include: satellite imagery from USGS (<http://www.usgs.gov/pubprod/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>), as well as aerial images (Google Earth imagery), free Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/content/data-sets> or ASTER GDEM <http://www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp/search.jsp> and vector layers available from the *Department of Geography, Geology and Landscape Ecology*. Any other available geodata sources will be considered as well (incl. descriptive data, articles and materials from the library of the *Matej Bel University, Department of*

§ 2. 15 July – 01 August. GIS Mapping

Creation of thematic maps in *ArcGIS* (if software is available) and/or *ILWIS*: landscapes, land cover changes in Slovakia.

Basic ground layers will include following features:

- Ground layer showing relief, based on DEM, satellite images and topographic maps
- Geomorphology of Tatra Mountains (mostly from DEM, and/or available vector layers)
- Hydrographic network
- Distribution of population in mountainous regions of Tatra Mountains
- Satellite images of the mountains taken in different time, for analysis of landscape dynamics in the last 10-20 years
- Landscape patterns and land cover types in Tatra Mountains.

All layers will be geo-referenced and presented in a compatible way, to enable their further using. In this working step we plan to fulfill all necessary image processing, spatial analysis of the thematic layers and, if necessary, creation of thematic layers anew, relevant for studies of the environmental dynamic of landscapes (based on *Spatial Analyst* in *ArcGIS*).

§ 3. 01. August – 15. August. Analysis of Landscape Dynamics and Land Cover Changes

1. Image processing using supervised classification (ILWIS techniques)
2. Studies of the landscape land cover types in Tatra, landscape characteristics, land cover types and land use patterns, as well as geomorphological features of the relief.
3. Using cartographic methods, available data (aerial photographs, DEMs, vector layers and satellite images) will be overlaid to present the complex landscape situation at present and 10-20 years ago (time span 1990 - 2010).
4. The analysis of the environmental changes in the mountainous region of Tatra will be done based on the detected changes in landscape on various images.

§ 4. 15. August – 01. September. Preparing final report and article

1. Writing article for the publication in scientific journal (Natural Sciences):
“*Mapping dynamic of the environmental changes in landscapes of Tatra Mountains*”.
2. Preparing final report for the NSP.

02nd of May, 2011.

Scientific chief:
Prof. Dr. Alfonz Gajdoš

Visiting researcher:
Polina Lemenkova, M.Sc